

What is the CoMSES Network?

→ comses.net

A Trusted Digital Repository of Computational Models

- Houses over 1000 individual models
- Peer review of computational models
- DOI minting and badging
- Interoperable software metadata
- Integration with the open science graph (ORCID, ROR, CodeMeta)

A Collection of Software Tools for Modelers

- FAIRification of model software and data
- Containerization and HPC recipes
- LLM applications

A Global Community of Social and Ecological Scientists

- Community events, news, and jobs
- 3700 active members

Curated Resources and Educational Content

- Computational modeling training
- Guidance on adopting FAIR principles and good software development practices
- Curated information resources for software frameworks, journals, and educational materials

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Peer reviewed **Viable North Sea (ViNoS): A NetLogo Agent-based Model of German Small-scale Fisheries**

Carsten Lemmen · Serra Örey · Sascha Hokamp · Wolfgang Nikolaus Probst · Jürgen Scheffran · Jeun Seo · Verena Mühlberger | Published Thursday, May 25, 2023 | Last modified Tuesday, December 05, 2023

Viable North Sea (ViNoS) is an Agent-based Model of the German North Sea Small-scale Fisheries in a Social-Ecological Systems framework focussing on the adaptive behaviour of fishers facing regulatory, economic, and resource changes...

[marine protected areas](#) [North Sea](#) [offshore wind](#) [shrimp](#) [fishery](#)

Peer reviewed **Evolutionary Economic Learning Simulation: A Genetic Algorithm for Dynamic 2x2 Strategic-Form Games in Python**

Vinicius Ferraz · Thomas Pitz | Published Friday, April 08, 2022

This project combines game theory and genetic algorithms in a simulation model for evolutionary learning and strategic behavior...

[learning](#) [evolutionary game theory](#) [behavioral game theory](#) [artificial intelligence](#) [genetic algorithm](#)

Peer reviewed **Price Evolution with Expectations**

Applegate · Gesine Steudel · Armin Haas · Carlo Jaeger | Published Friday, September 10, 2021

The Price Evolution with Expectations model provides the opportunity to explore the question of non-equilibrium market dynamics, and how and under which conditions an economic system converges to the classically defined economic equilibrium...

[price](#) [evolutionary economics](#) [complexity economics](#) [multiple equilibria](#)

Publish a model

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Peer Review Status

Reviewed

Not Reviewed

Any

Programming Languages

Python (5)

Agent-Based Modelling - Software engineering - Information Systems and Social Networks (1)

NetLogo (1)

Netlogo (1)

Python 3 (1)

R (1)

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CHIME ABM of Hurricane Evacuation 2.1.0

Submitted by [Sean Bergin](#) · Published Jan 04, 2022 · Last modified Jan 04, 2022

[decision model](#) [risk](#) [hurricanes](#)

[Download Version 2.1.0](#)

The Communicating Hazard Information in the Modern Environment (CHIME) agent-based model (ABM) is a Netlogo program that facilitates the analysis of information flow and protective decisions across space and time during hazardous weather events. CHIME ABM provides a platform for testing hypotheses about collective human responses to weather forecasts and information flow, using empirical data from historical hurricanes. The model uses real world geographical and hurricane data to set the boundaries of the simulation, and it uses historical hurricane forecast information from the National Hurricane Center to initiate forecast information flow to citizen agents in the model.

Release Notes

This release is an updated version of the CHIME ABM previously published by Joshua Watts and available here: <https://doi.org/10.25937/hbnh-af93>

This version has a wide array of small and large differences which include:

- New Hurricanes
- A procedure to read in the new hurricane forecast format from the National Hurricane Center
- The inclusion of census data for Florida which can be used to modify the behavior of agents
- A detailed code documentation and optimization

Cite this Model

Sean Bergin, C Michael Barton, Joshua Watts, Joshua Alland, Rebecca Morss (2022, January 04). "CHIME ABM of Hurricane Evacuation" (Version 2.1.0). *CoMSES Computational Model Library*. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.25937/fqah-sj53>

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External Repository

github.com/comses/chime-abm

DOI

[10.25937/fqah-sj53](https://doi.org/10.25937/fqah-sj53)

Model Version

2.1.0

License

GPL-3.0

Programming Language

Logo

Software Framework

NetLogo

Operating System

Operating System Independent

Publish Date

Tuesday, January 04, 2022

Last Updated

Thursday, January 06, 2022

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 PEER REVIEWED

 OPEN CODE